

Spectroscopic and thermodynamic studies on the interaction of atorvastatin and clomiphene drugs with bovine serum albumin in aqueous buffer

M. Suganthi and Kuppanagounder P. Elango*

Department of Chemistry, Gandhigram Rural Institute (Deemed University), Gandhigram-624 302, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail: drkpelango@rediffmail.com Fax: 91-451-2454466

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The interaction between bovine serum albumin (BSA) and atorvastatin (ATR) and clomiphene citrate (CC) drugs is investigated using various spectral techniques. The results revealed the existence of strong interactions between the drugs and the protein. The entropy changes indicate that ATR binds with the protein through van der Waals forces and H-bonding interactions, while CC binds spontaneously through hydrophobic forces. The results of these combined spectroscopic studies indicate conformational change of BSA, with an increase in α -helical content, after binding to the drugs. The molecular docking studies indicate that the drugs bind to BSA possibly in the subdomain IIA.

Keywords: Atorvastatin, clomiphene citrate, serum albumin, spectroscopic, docking.

Introduction

Serum albumins, the most abundant carrier proteins in blood plasma, play an important role in the transportation and distribution of many ligands such as drugs, amino acids, fatty acids, etc. in blood. Also, they have many important physiological functions¹⁻³. It is well known that the absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion of drugs are strongly affected by the protein-drug interactions in plasma. Thus, in recent years, increasing research attentions have been aroused on the study of interactions between proteins and drugs^{4,5}. Human and bovine serum albumins display approximately 76% sequence homology, the three dimensional structure of bovine serum albumin (BSA) is believed to be similar to that of human serum albumin (HAS) and hence BSA is often used as model protein in research work⁶⁻⁸.

The drug atorvastatin (ATR) is commonly used for the treatment of dyslipidaemia, while a reduction in low density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) was observed in many of these studies⁹. Clomiphene citrate (CC) is a compound widely used in ovulation induction¹⁰. The chemical structures of these drugs are given in Fig. 1.

Survey of literature revealed that no attempt was made to investigate the interaction between these two drugs and

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of the drugs.

serum albumin. The main objective, therefore, of the present endeavor is the detailed study on the interaction of BSA with atorvastatin and clomiphene citrate drugs in biological conditions using various spectral techniques such as UV-Vis, fluorescence and circular dichroism. The thermodynamic aspects of the interactions are studied and discussed. The binding characteristics of the drugs with BSA were also investigated by molecular docking study.

Experimental

Materials:

Commercially available bovine serum albumin was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, India and was used as received. The drugs atorvastatin and clomiphene citrate were obtained as gift samples from locally available pharmaceutical company. The purity of the drugs was checked by its melting point. Double distilled water was used throughout the work and the second distillation was carried out using alkaline permanganate. 0.1 M phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 was prepared in double distilled water. The stock solutions of BSA and drugs were prepared in an aqueous solution of 0.1 M phosphate buffer.

Methods:

The electronic absorption spectra were recorded on a JASCO (V630, Japan) double beam spectrophotometer using 10 mm path length quartz cuvette. Fluorescence spectra were recorded on a JASCO (FP-8500, Japan) spectrophotometer. The excitation and emission slit widths were 10 nm. Circular dichroism (CD) measurements were performed with a JASCO-810 spectropolarimeter using a 0.1 cm path length quartz cell. The CD spectra were recorded in the range of 200–250 nm. All observed spectra were baseline subtracted for buffer solution and the α -helical content was calculated on the basis of molar ellipticity value. The molecular docking study was performed using Molegro Virtual Docker (MolDock) software.

Results and discussion

UV-Vis spectral studies:

To explore the conformational changes of BSA and complex formation between BSA and the drugs, UV-Vis absorption spectra of BSA in the absence and presence of the drugs were recorded in 0.1 M phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 at 298 K. The spectra thus obtained are shown in Fig. 2. It is evident from the figure that the free BSA exhibited a peak at 277 nm corresponding to the absorption of tryptophan and tyrosine residues^{11,12}. On incremental addition of the drug, in both the cases, the intensity of absorption of BSA was found to increase. It is well known that there is a significant relationship between the absorption spectra of BSA and the chro-

Fig. 2. UV-Vis spectra of BSA (1×10^{-5} M) in the absence and presence of incremental addition (0 to 2.5×10^{-5} M) of (A) ATR and (B) CC.

mophores of the protein (and the conformation of the protein)¹³. Therefore, the variation observed in the absorption spectra of BSA indicated that these drugs bind to BSA forming a complex and induce conformational changes in BSA molecule.

Fluorescence spectral studies:

Fluorescence spectroscopy has been widely used as a powerful tool in the study of molecular interactions between ligands and BSA as it can give vital information on the binding of these ligands with the protein¹⁴. The fluorescence spectra of BSA, in the absence and presence of increasing concentrations of the drugs, were recorded in the range of 290–500 nm at the excitation wavelength of 295 nm. The choice of 295 nm as the excitation wavelength is to avoid the contribution of tyrosine residues¹⁵. The fluorescence spectra thus

obtained for the two drug systems at three different temperatures (298, 308 and 318 K) are shown in Fig. 3. As seen from the figures that the emission spectrum of BSA in the absence of these drugs showed an emission at 348 nm. Further, in both the cases, upon addition of increasing concentrations of the drugs the fluorescence intensity of BSA decreased drastically suggesting the formation of a complex between the protein and the drugs¹⁶.

The fluorescence quenching is known to occur mainly by formation of a complex (static quenching) or by collisional quenching process (dynamic quenching) between the fluorophore and quencher. In the present study, the decrease

Fig. 3. Emission spectra of BSA ($1 \times 10^{-6} M$) in the absence and presence of incremental addition (0 to $2.5 \times 10^{-5} M$) of (A) ATR and (B) CC at 298 K.

in emission intensity of BSA at 348 nm in the presence of the ATR and CC was delineated using the Stern-Volmer equation¹⁷.

$$F_0/F = 1 + K_{SV} [Q] \quad (1)$$

where F_0 and F are the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of the quencher $[Q]$ and K_{SV} is the Stern-Volmer quenching constant which measures the efficiency of quenching. The Stern-Volmer plots were found to be linear ($r > 0.99$) in the concentration range under investigation. The values of K_{SV} were inversely related with temperature (Table 1), which indicated that the most likely mechanism of interaction between BSA and the drugs, in the present study, would be static quenching with BSA-drug complex formation at ground state, rather than dynamic quenching¹⁸.

Table 1. Stern-Volmer constants for the BSA-drug systems

Temp. (K)	BSA-ATR		BSA-CC	
	r	$K_{SV} (L \text{ mol}^{-1})$	r	$K_{SV} (L \text{ mol}^{-1})$
298	0.999	3.6×10^4	0.994	2.6×10^4
308	0.996	3.4×10^4	0.991	2.3×10^4
318	0.997	3.2×10^4	0.998	1.9×10^4

The fluorescence quenching due to the formation of a complex between BSA and the drugs was further used to determine the binding parameters. The values of binding constant (K_a) and number of binding sites (n) were calculated from the following equation¹⁹.

$$\log [(F_0 - F)/F] = \log K_a + n \log [Q] \quad (2)$$

where F_0 and F are the fluorescence intensity of BSA in the absence and presence of the drugs, respectively. The plot of $\log [(F_0 - F)/F]$ versus $\log [Q]$ gave a straight line, with excellent correlation coefficient ($r > 0.99$) values at three temperatures. The statistical results of the plots and the values of binding parameters calculated are collected in Table 2. The results in Table 2 indicated that the drugs bind strongly to BSA. The value of n nearly equals to 1, which indicated that there is one binding site in BSA for the drugs. The binding constant values obtained in the present study are comparable and even higher than that for other drug-serum albumin interactions reported in literature (in $L \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 298 K): methimazole (4×10^4) by Afrin *et al.*²⁰, phacolysin (1×10^5) by Yu *et al.*²¹, aristolochic acid I (4×10^5) by Wu *et al.*²², 5-fluorouracil (3×10^4) by Chinnathambi *et al.*¹⁶, oxaliplatin (3.7×10^3) by Yue *et al.*²³, levofloxacin (9×10^4), sparfloxacin (10.5×10^4),

Table 2. Binding and thermodynamic parameters for the interaction of BSA and the drugs

Drug	Temp. (K)	r	K_a (L mol ⁻¹)	n	ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)
ATR	298	0.999	1716×10^4	1.3	-243	-679	-41
	308	0.990	63×10^4	1.2			
	318	0.996	3×10^4	0.99			
CC	298	0.999	1×10^5	1.2	235	885	-29
	308	0.995	13×10^5	1.3			
	318	0.995	574×10^5	1.3			

ciprofloxacin.HCl (5.7×10^4), enrofloxacin (4.6×10^4) by Seedher *et al.*²⁴.

Thermodynamic parameters:

The forces enabling the binding of a drug with biomolecules are composed of various weak non-covalent interactions such as van der Waals, hydrophobic, electrostatic and H-bonding interactions. The thermodynamic parameters such as enthalpy (ΔH°), entropy (ΔS°) and free energy (ΔG°) changes of complexation reaction are the main evidence for confirming the binding force²⁵. Therefore, to characterize the acting force between BSA and the drugs, the temperature dependence of binding constants was studied. The temperatures chosen for the study were 298, 308 and 318 K, at which BSA does not undergo any structural degradation. The thermodynamic parameters were determined using van't Hoff equation.

$$\ln K_a = -\Delta H^\circ/RT + \Delta S^\circ/R \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T \Delta S^\circ \quad (4)$$

where, K_a is the binding constant at a given temperature and R is the gas constant. In both the cases, a plot of $\ln K_a$ versus $1/T$ is linear with correlation coefficient $r > 0.99$. The thermodynamic parameters thus computed for the interaction of BSA with the two drugs ATR and CC are also collected in Table 2.

It is evident from the results that, in both the cases, the negative free energy change indicate the spontaneity of the binding of the drugs with BSA molecule under standard conditions⁶. According to Ross and Subramanian, a positive value of entropy change is frequently taken as an evidence for the existence of hydrophobic interaction²⁶. Thus in the present study positive values of enthalpy and entropy changes indicated that hydrophobic forces played the major role in BSA-

CC interaction and the formation BSA-CC complex was an endothermic process. On the other hand, in the case of ATR drug system, the negative values enthalpy and entropy changes indicated that the binding of ATR drug to BSA molecule is an exothermic process and might involve both van der Waals forces and H-bonding interactions²⁶.

Conformational investigation:

Synchronous fluorescence spectral studies:

The fluorescence of protein molecule comes from tryptophan and tyrosine residues and the emission shifts of these residues could be employed to examine the conformational changes of protein. Lloyd *et al.* have proposed the use of synchronous fluorescence spectroscopy technique to analyze the conformational changes that occur when BSA binds to a ligand²⁷. In general, for protein molecules, when the $\Delta\lambda = 15$ nm is fixed, the fluorescence spectrum characteristic of tyrosine residue will be observed, while when the $\Delta\lambda = 60$ nm is fixed, the fluorescence spectrum characteristic of tryptophan residue will be observed²¹. In the present study, synchronous fluorescence spectroscopy technique was employed to get information about the binding of the chosen drugs with BSA molecule. The synchronous fluorescence spectra of BSA obtained with incremental addition of ATR drug is shown in Fig. 4.

The results showed that upon addition of ATR drug to BSA solution, the fluorescence of BSA was quenched indicating that the micro environment of tryptophan and tyrosine residues is disturbed. A relatively larger extent of quenching was observed when $\Delta\lambda = 60$ nm than that of $\Delta\lambda = 15$ nm, suggesting that ATR drug is closer to tryptophan residue compared to tyrosine residue and the binding sites are mainly focused on tryptophan residue. In the synchronous fluores-

Fig. 4. Synchronous fluorescence spectra of BSA ($1 \times 10^{-6} M$) with incremental addition (0 to $2.5 \times 10^{-5} M$) of ATR at (A) $\Delta\lambda = 15$ nm and (B) $\Delta\lambda = 60$ nm at 298 K.

Fig. 5. Synchronous fluorescence spectra of BSA ($1 \times 10^{-6} M$) with incremental addition (0 to $2.5 \times 10^{-5} M$) of CC at (A) $\Delta\lambda = 15$ nm and (B) $\Delta\lambda = 60$ nm at 298 K.

cence spectra obtained with both $\Delta\lambda = 15$ and $\Delta\lambda = 60$ nm, the maximum emission wavelength experienced a very weak red shift (~ 2 nm) indicating that the polarity around the tryptophan residue was increased and the hydrophobicity was decreased²⁸. Similar very weak red shift in wavelength was reported by Tunc *et al.*²⁵ in the study of interaction of carbofuran and amitrol herbicides with HSA. The synchronous fluorescence spectra of BSA obtained with incremental addition of drug CC is shown in Fig. 5. It is evident from the figure that the maximum wavelength emission of both the tryptophan and tyrosine residues has a very slight blue shift (~ 2 nm), indicating that the polarity around these residues decreased and the hydrophobicity increased. Parallel blue-shift of emission maximum was observed by Guo *et al.*³ during the interaction of *p*-nitrophenol with BSA. The results of

synchronous fluorescence spectral analysis indicated that the binding of the chosen drugs to BSA caused a change in the conformation of BSA molecule.

Three dimensional fluorescence spectral studies:

In order to get more scientific and credible insight into the conformational and micro environmental changes of BSA molecule upon complexation with the drugs, three dimensional fluorescence spectral studies were also carried out. The main advantage of this spectral analysis is that detailed information regarding the emission characteristics can be obtained by changing the excitation and emission wavelengths simultaneously. The three dimensional fluorescence spectra along with contour maps of BSA and its drugs complexes are shown in Fig. 6 and the corresponding characteristic parameters are collected in Table 3.

Table 3. Three dimensional fluorescence spectral characteristic parameters of BSA and its drug complexes

System	Parameter	Peak 1	Peak 2
BSA	Peak position ($\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em}$, nm)	280/335	230/330
	Fluorescence intensity	3849	3171
	Stokes shift ($\Delta\lambda$ /nm)	55	100
BSA-ATR	Peak position ($\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em}$, nm)	280/335	230/330
	Fluorescence intensity	2256	2207
	Stokes shift ($\Delta\lambda$ /nm)	55	100
BSA-CC	Peak position ($\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em}$, nm)	280/365	230/330
	Fluorescence intensity	2805	2777
	Stokes shift ($\Delta\lambda$ /nm)	85	100

In Fig. 6A, for BSA molecule, the peak 1 ($\lambda_{ex} = 280$, $\lambda_{em} = 335$ nm) corresponds to the emission characteristics of tyrosine and tryptophan residues and peak 2 ($\lambda_{ex} = 230$, $\lambda_{em} = 330$ nm) mainly reveal the emission behavior of polypeptide backbone structures of the molecule, whose intensity is related with the secondary structure of protein²⁸. The results of three dimensional fluorescence spectral analyses indicated that, in both the cases, the emission peaks 1 and 2 of BSA had been quenched with the addition of in-

Fig. 6. Three dimensional fluorescence spectra and contour maps of (A) BSA, (B) BSA-ATR complex and (C) BSA-CC complex. [BSA] = 1×10^{-6} M, [Drug] = 1×10^{-6} M.

cremental amounts of the drugs ATR and CC. As shown in the Table 3, the maximum emission wavelength of BSA was also red shifted upon addition of the drug CC. The above discussions and analysis of peaks 1 and 2 revealed that the binding of the drugs (ATR and CC) with BSA induced some changes in micro environment and conformation of BSA molecule.

CD spectral studies:

To further explore the structural changes of BSA upon addition of the chosen drugs, circular dichroism experiment was also carried out in 0.1 M phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 at room temperature. The CD spectra obtained for BSA and its drug complexes are depicted in Fig. 7. The CD spectrum of BSA showed two negative bands in the far-UV region at 208 and 220 nm, which are characteristics of α -helical structure of proteins and are due to the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the peptide bond of α -helices²⁹. The CD spectral results were quantita-

Fig. 7. CD spectra of BSA and its drug complexes obtained in 0.1 M phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 at room temperature. [BSA] = 1×10^{-6} M; [Drug] = 1×10^{-6} M.

tively expressed in terms of mean residue ellipticity (MRE) in $\text{deg cm}^2 \text{dmol}^{-1}$ according to the following equation.

$$\text{MRE} = \text{observed CD (mdeg)} / [C_p n l / 10] \quad (5)$$

where C_p is the molar concentration of the BSA, n is the number of amino acid residues in BSA and l is the path length. The α -helical contents of free and bound BSA were calculated from MRE values at 208 nm using the following equation.

$$\alpha\text{-helix (\%)} =$$

$$[(-\text{MRE}_{208} - 4000) / (33000 - 4000)] \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where MRE_{208} is the observed MRE value at 208 nm, 4000 is the MRE of the β -form and random coil conformation cross at 208 nm and 33000 is the MRE value of pure α -helix at 208 nm. Using the eqs. (5) and (6), the calculated results exhibited an increase in α -helix structure from 54.3 to 60.2% at BSA/ATR molar ratio of 1:1 and to 59.2% at BSA/CC molar ratio of 1:1, thus produced a stabilizing effect on the secondary structure. Similar increase of the α -helical secondary structure content was reported by Seyed Dorraji *et al.*³⁰ in the study of interaction of deferiprone drug with HSA and Chunmei *et al.*³¹ in the interaction of Hg^{II} ion with BSA. From the above results it is apparent that the binding of the chosen drugs with BSA causes a conformation change of the protein molecule, with a slight gain of α -helical stability.

Energy transfer between BSA and the drugs:

The foregoing results and discussion indicated the formation of complexes between the drugs and BSA molecule. Investigation of energy transfer that may occur between the partners in the complex and consequently the estimation of the binding distance between them can provide information about the formation of such a complex. In the present study, the fluorescence quenching of BSA after binding with the drugs indicated that the energy transfer between them has occurred. The overlap of the emission spectrum of BSA and the absorption spectrum of the drugs, which is the essential prerequisite for the possibility of an energy transfer mechanism, was observed for both the systems (Fig. 8).

According to the Förster's non-radiative energy transfer theory³², the efficiency of energy transfer (E) is related to the distance between donor and acceptor by:

$$E = R_0^6 / (R_0^6 + r^6) = 1 - F/F_0 \quad (7)$$

where r is the distance between donor and acceptor and R_0 is the critical distance when the transfer efficiency is 50%. F_0 and F were the fluorescence intensities of BSA at 342 nm in the absence and presence of drug, respectively.

R_0 can be calculated by:

$$R_0 = 0.211 [k^2 n^{-4} \Phi_D J(\lambda)]^{1/6} \quad (8)$$

where n is the refractive index of the medium, k^2 is the orientation factor and Φ_D is the quantum yield of the donor³³. For BSA, the values of k^2 , n and Φ_D are 2/3, 1.336 and 0.118,

Fig. 8. Spectral overlaps of the fluorescence spectrum of BSA with the absorption spectrum of (A) ATR and (B) CC.

respectively³⁴. J is the overlap integral of the fluorescence emission spectrum of BSA with the absorption spectrum of drug (Fig. 8), which is given by:

$$J(\lambda) = \int F_d(\lambda) \epsilon_a(\lambda) \lambda^4 d\lambda / \int F_d(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (9)$$

where $F_d(\lambda)$ and $\epsilon_a(\lambda)$ represent the fluorescence intensity of the donor and the molar extinction coefficient of the acceptor, respectively, at the wavelength λ . The value of J can be evaluated by integrating the overlapped portion of the spectra in the Fig. 8. Using the above eqs. (7) – (9), R_0 , E and r_0 were calculated and the values for ATR and CC drugs were found to be $R_0 = 4.7$ nm, $E = 0.43$ and $r_0 = 4.9$ nm and $R_0 = 3.8$ nm, $E = 0.31$ and $r_0 = 4.4$ nm, respectively. In the present study, the donor acceptor distance (r_0) is less than 8 nm, indicating that the energy transfer from BSA to the drug

occurs with high possibility³⁵. Thus, the formation of BSA-drug complexes is through energy transfer that quenched the fluorescence of BSA.

Molecular docking study:

A docking program was run to substantiate the experimental results and to stimulate the binding mode between BSA and the chosen drugs (ATR and CC). As seen from Fig. 9, the chosen drugs could bind to BSA in the subdomain IIA, which is a main binding domain and most ligands exhibit their unique biological activity by binding to this domain. Further, it is also evident from the figure that the drug molecules were located within the binding pocket and were adjacent to hydrophobic residues Asp129, His145, Leu189, Glu182,

Fig. 9. (A) Binding site of ATR on BSA and (B) binding site of CC on BSA (BSA is shown in cartoon and the drugs are represented using spheres).

Tyr160, Trp134, Trp212 *etc.* of subdomain IIA of BSA³⁵. From the docking study, out of various possibilities the stable interacting conformation is the one having the drugs in near vicinity of Trp212, which is strongly in agreement with the results of the fluorescence spectral studies carried out with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 295 \text{ nm}$ corresponding to Trp212 residue³⁵. The free energy changes, calculated from fluorescence spectral results, for the binding of ATR and CC to BSA are -41 and -29 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively. The ΔG° values calculated for the BSA-ATR and BSA-CC systems from computational studies are -62 and -65 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively. The difference in the computed ΔG° values from the experimental ΔG° values may be explained based on the fact that X-ray structure of BSA from crystals is different from that of the aqueous system used in the present study²³.

Conclusion

The binding of atorvastatin (ATR) and clomiphene citrate (CC) drugs to BSA was investigated by employing UV-Vis, fluorescence and circular dichroism spectral techniques under physiological condition. The results showed that the drugs bind to BSA with high affinity and quenches the emission of BSA efficiently through static quenching mechanism. The negative free energy change in both BSA-ATR and BSA-CC cases suggested that the protein-drug interaction is a spontaneous process. The enthalpy and entropy changes of these systems revealed the nature of the forces acting in the binding process. The three dimensional fluorescence spectral analyses indicated that the binding of the drugs with BSA induced some changes in micro environment and conformation of BSA molecule. CD spectroscopy results showed that the secondary structure of BSA is stabilized after the drugs bind to BSA. Based on the theory of Förster's non-radiation energy transfer, the binding distance, in both the cases, was calculated to be $< 8 \text{ nm}$ indicating energy transfer between BSA and the drugs is taking place with high probability. Moreover, molecular docking results suggested that ATR and CC bind to BSA into the hydrophobic cavity of subdomain IIA. This work has provided reasonable model to understand the transportation and distribution of the chosen drugs when it spreads into the human blood serum.

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